

THE ROLE OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN OVERCOMING INTERCULTURAL CONFLICTS

Qodirova Dilnoza Xoliq qizi

Student of Media and Communication faculty, UzSWLU

Tel number: +998901808002

Email: qodirovadilnoza0922@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6969026>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st August 2022

Accepted: 03rd August 2022

Online: 05th August 2022

KEY WORDS

Intercultural communication, biculturalism, multiculturalism, intercultural conflicts, cultural competence culture, non-verbal communication.

The study of communication between people of other cultures and social groups, as well as how culture influences communication, is known as intercultural communication. It refers to the wide range of communication procedures and issues that inevitably arise when people from various religious, social, ethnic and educational backgrounds work together in an organization or social context. It aims to comprehend how people from other countries and cultures act, communicate, and view the world around them in this way. Intercultural communication focuses on recognizing and respecting persons who have different cultural backgrounds. The goal is mutual adaptation between two or more separate cultures, rather than complete integration, which leads to biculturalism/ multiculturalism. It encourages the development of cultural

ABSTRACT

People can learn new languages and traditions, tolerate non-verbal communication disparities, and prepare for intercultural encounters. However, the primary goal should be to develop intercultural communication competency, or the ability to manage important aspects of intercultural communication. In this paper, I will discuss the concept of communication, particularly nonverbal communication, and its characteristics in communicating a message across cultures.

sensitivity and enables for cross-cultural empathy.

Today's world is marked by an increasing number of interactions that result in communication between people of various languages and cultural backgrounds. Contact with people from other cultures is sometimes stressful and fraught with miscommunication. Good intentions and a nice demeanor do not appear to be enough. One of the most important aspects of communication is respect for other cultures. No one should look down on people who have different habits, languages, or civilizations; instead, attempt to comprehend what and how they see the world through their eyes. Contacts in the fields of tourism, education, science, and entertainment, as well as business, politics, and immigration, facilitate cross-cultural communication. Because the group to

which a person belongs is distinct, communication in all of these cross-cultural encounters must be constructive and free of misunderstandings. New sorts of relationships are currently posing communication issues that few people are prepared to.

When a person from one culture sends a message to be processed by someone from another culture, intercultural communication happens. The subject of intercultural communication is hampered by a major issue, as the linguistic phrase culture frequently causes confusion. To begin with, it refers to a huge group of people and what they share in common, such as their history, language, or geographic location. When people refer to the Japanese, Chinese, Americans, British, and so on, they are referring to what these groups have in common and what disparities exist among their members. When discussing such big groups, it is vital to avoid the problem of overgeneralization by referring to world culture in places where it does not apply, particularly in discourse of intercultural communication.

Individual conversation is referred to as discourse. Culture, on the other hand, is a secondary consideration. It is a set of guidelines for living and working in a society. Individuals do not converse with different cultures. Individuals with either an American or a French heritage can only communicate with each other through their respective cultures. This branch of research examines how people from various cultural backgrounds communicate with one another and across cultures in similar and distinct ways. Culture is a collection of beliefs, ideas, customs, general behavior, festivals, cuisine, attitudes, and even clothing styles that vary by country.

People from the same country share cultural commonalities, yet there are also differences, particularly in geographical locations within a country. Cultures vary over time, but people who migrate from one culture to another do not change their cultures. As a result, cross-cultural communication necessitates prudence.

Culture is a discursive space that is continually changing, not a fixed identity. As a result, cultural interactions are a complicated interaction of entities that are always negotiating their own identities. Culture is a human creation as well, a system of symbols through which man gives meaning to his own experiences. This establishes one's identity and worldview. As a result, cultures are seen as manifestations of differences. Culture fosters a sense of belonging, identity, and inclusion, and so implies exclusion and borders. These boundaries are not as well defined as national borders, yet they are crucial to cultural interactions.

The link between cultures is defined by the meaning at these borders. These constrained spaces are discursive, allowing for debates, agreements, and compromises. Maintaining a good balance between the forces of individualism and community to offer a common sense of identity while preserving individual dignity, freedom, and creativity is also part of cultural communication. As each conversation includes culture-specific characteristics, cultural communication entails the negotiation of cultural conventions. Nonverbal communication is a significant aspect of cultural contact.

No two persons are the same, regardless of ethnicity or life experiences, and everyone has different values, views, or assumptions than others. These values and experiences

are formed by our life events, which shape our conduct and decisions. To better comprehend a person's worldview, we must assume that judgments of culturally distinct conduct are likely to be ethnocentric, and that they will interact with the communication required to learn about the worldview context in which the behavior must be evaluated in any event. People in some worldviews can find similar ground on which to build shared understanding and respect.

In Conclusion, the first step toward a better understanding and improved intercultural

communication is to be aware of all of the challenges listed. Long-standing habits or thought patterns must be changed before progress can be made. The growing demand for global understanding places us all in a position to contribute our best efforts. A person should be able to navigate his way into close proximity to foreign ideals, attitudes, and customs. He should be able to collaborate with them without sacrificing his own principles in the pursuit of a better society.

References:

1. Luring, Jacob (2011). Intercultural Organizational Communication: The Social Organizing of Interaction in International Encounters. Journal of Business Communication.
2. Barna, Laray. Stumbling blocks in Intercultural Communication, in Samovar, L.A. Porter: Intercultural Communication: A Reader, Wadsworth Publishing Company, Belmont, CA, 1994.
3. Cit, Mc Daniel, E. Samovar, L. Porter: Understanding Intercultural Communication. The Working Principles. 2009.
4. Scollon, Ronald. Scollon, Suzanne. Intercultural communication: a discourse approach, Blackwells Publishing Ltd. Oxford 2001.
5. Clifford, James. On Orientalism in: The Predicament of Culture: Twentieth Century Ethnography, Literature and Art, Harvard University Press, Cambridge. 1988.
6. Watson, Ian: Negotiating Cultures. Eugenio Barba and intercultural debate. Manchester University Press, New York. 2002.